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Universitätsklinikum Mannheim

Master Thesis

**A Monte Carlo simulation framework for modelling Artis
Zeego CBCT using GATE.**

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Date of submission: November 22, 2019

Declaration

I hereby declare that the work presented in this M.Sc. dissertation is a genuine work done by me under close guidance and supervision of my supervisor. Information derived from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of references is provided. No part of this dissertation was previously presented for another degree at this or any other institution.

Mannheim, November 26, 2019

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Acknowledgement

I would like to thank prof. Schad and prof. Zöllner for giving me the opportunity to work on Monte Carlo simulation research field in the CKM department at UMM. I am thankful to my mentors at the university of applied science Mannheim, prof. Heger and prof. Niemz for the discussions and guidance to carry out the research work. Furthermore, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor Mr. Tom Russ for the knowledge, motivation and the continuous support he has shown right from the very first day at UMM. His guidance has helped me throughout my research work and with the writing of this thesis. Thanks to all my colleagues at H35 and H8 for the enjoyable atmosphere and right working environment. This short period of experience will be cherished for the rest of my life. Finally, I wish to express my great gratitude to my family and friends for their constant support and encouragement during my M.Sc. studies.

Abstract

For task-specific images taken for minimally invasive interventions, limiting the acquisition angle or reducing the number of projections of the cone-beam CT (CBCT) system can lead to efficient minimization of patient dosage. Geant4 application for tomographic emission (GATE) is dedicated to modelling of medical imaging systems. It facilitates Monte Carlo (MC) simulation through an easy-to-use script code and does not require prior C++ knowledge. For accurate CT projections, the material and geometry specifications of the filter, collimator, source and the detector are modeled as close as possible to an interventional CBCT scanner (Artis zeego, Siemens Healthineers, Forchheim, Germany). Simulations were performed using a patient realistic XCAT phantom, which depicts the cardio-torso region of the body and a water cylinder whose simulation results were compared to actual measurement results obtained from the Artis zeego CBCT scanner. The simulation runtime was reduced from multiple weeks on one CPU down to 2-3 days by dividing the simulation into 500 smaller tasks and parallelly executing them on EGI's (European Grid Infrastructure) computer cluster through the Gate-Lab platform. GATE Simulation results showed acceptable similarity with the Artis zeego measurement results. The proposed GATE framework enables accelerated simulation of CT projections of arbitrary source-detector orbits and can incorporate patient anatomy.

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Associated Publications

Tom Russ, Aimen M. Abdelrehim, Dominik F. Bauer, Lothar R. Schad, Frank G. Zöllner Khanlian Chung . Framework for image quality and physical dose predictions of arbitrary CBCT source-detector trajectories with GATE. In 4th Conference on Image-Guided Interventions, 2019

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List of Abbreviations

CT	Computed Tomography
CBCT	Cone Beam Computed Tomography
EI	Electronic Ionization
GATE	Geant4 Application for Tomographic Emission
GPS	General Particle Source
LCG	Linear Congruential generators
LFG	Lagged Fibonacci generators
MCNP	Monte Carlo N-particle Transport Code
MIS	Minimal Invasive Surgery
MT	Monte Carlo
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
PE	Photoelectric Effect
PPE	Probability Distribution Function
RNG	Random Number Generator
PRNG	Pseudo Random Number Generator
ROC	Read-out Chip
TFT	Thin-film Transistor
VRT	Variance Reduction Technique

1 Introduction

CT images are increasingly demanded by physicians for the purpose of diagnosis. In Minimal invasive surgery (MIS), which is one of the fastest growing medical disciplines [1], these images are highly relied upon for real-time information on the patient's anatomy during an intervention. The popularity of the high quality CBCT 3D images has shown tremendous increase in the interventional rooms due to the high practicality of the C-arm machines. However, the rapid increase of CBCT has caused serious public concern with regards to ionizing radiation [2]. Experimental and epidemiological evidence has linked exposure to X-rays during CT exams with the development of solid organ cancers and leukaemia [3].

One of the methods to reduce X-ray dosage is to limit the angle of source-detector rotation around the body as in case of tomosynthesis. In most of the interventional cases, the CBCT images are used to control the position and the pathway of the medical instrument inside the patient. During liver biopsy for example, the pathway of the biopsy needle is directed based on the patient-specific image information received from the CBCT. For such applications it is not necessary to capture a 3D image by applying 360° X-ray projections. A task-specific image, that includes relevant information about high-contrast surgical instruments obtained by using limited number of projections from narrow angular range can be sufficient. This technique has a great potential for significant dose reduction.

To develop and validate the radiation reduction technique CBCT computer simulations (CS) are commonly utilized. CS avoids the risk of experimental exposure of ionizing radiation on patients. This is achieved by bulky simulations using mathematical modeling [4, 5] or MC simulations [6, 7].

The MC method is widely used for solving scientific problems involving statistical processes and is particularly well suited for medical physics and biomedical engineering applications due to the stochastic nature of radiation emission, transport and detection processes. The general idea of MC analysis is to create a model of the CBCT imaging

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system and to calculate the physics interactions of X-rays with matter using random sampling of probability density functions for each X-ray photon. The MC technique often relies on open-source MC codes such as MCNP[8], EGS4 [9] and GEANT4 [10].

Geant4 exploits advanced engineering technique for radiological modelling of an imaging system. X-ray generation, attenuation and detection can be modelled using this technique. GATE (Geant4 Application for Tomographic Emission) is based on Geant4 and requires no prior Fortran and C++ knowledge. GATE uses an easy-to-learn script language to design a large variability of experimental configurations, from the very simple to highly detailed. GATE plays a key role in the design of new medical imaging devices and in the optimization of acquisition protocols [11].

The main objective of this thesis is to create a CBCT framework based on the MC method using GATE. The developed framework is constructed to allow the simulation of CBCT images with alternative trajectories as in the case of tomosynthesis simulations and will allow to study the efficiency of the resulting images and the extent with which this technique can reduce dosage and therefore avoid the risk of cancer occurrence. Furthermore, it builds the foundation for dose evaluation to be implemented in the future.

The project is carried out at the Institute for Computer Assisted Clinical Medicine. The institute is an important contributor to the one stop-shop cancer diagnosis project carried out by the Mannheim Molecular Intervention Environment *M²OLIE* research center. For data acquisition and testing, the institute has access to C-arm CBCT (Artis zeego, Siemens Healthineers, Forchheim, Germany) to validate the GATE simulations with the real measurements.

2 Background

2.1 Computed Tomography

Computed tomography (CT) is an examination that uses X-ray and digital signal processing to obtain cross-sectional and three-dimensional images of the the human body. The X-ray source in CT is not fixed rather it rotates around the object being scanned. As the source rotates it shoots X-ray beams which are detected by the X-ray detector placed directly opposite to the source as seen in Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1: CT scanner with the X-ray source and the detectors shown in 3 positions [12]

The source and the detectors are rotated around the patient to obtain images from all directions. The table is then moved along the axis of the machine (z axis) for another set of images. These images are then combined using a complex computer algorithm to give 3D CT image of the organ under investigation.

The CT number ξ represents the photon attenuation coefficient of the tissue in a CT image, it involves the linear attenuation coefficient of pure water μ_w at STP (Standard Pressure and temperature) and is given in Hounsfield Units (HU).

$$\xi = \frac{\mu_t - \mu_w}{\mu_w} \times 1000 = (\hat{\mu}_t - 1) \times 1000 \quad (2.1)$$

2.2 X-ray Production and Detection

X-ray Production

X-ray is produced in the X-ray tube as seen in Figure 2.2. When an electron emitted from a cathode is accelerated with sufficient energy towards an anode. The subsequent emission will emit X-rays. The cathode is a filament that releases electrons when heated. Since electrons are produced in all directions, a "focusing cup" is used to aim the electrons to the anode. The anode is a heavy metal target such as tungsten. Tungsten is preferred over other materials because it has a high atomic number, i.e. larger nuclei, results in better X-ray production efficiency due to the fact that electrons have larger target. It has a high melting point which means the generated heat due to electron collision with anode wouldn't be enough to melt the Tungsten. Moreover, it has a high thermal conductivity which would increase the durability of the anode.

Figure 2.2: A schematic drawing of a basic rotating anode X-ray tube[13].

X-ray Detection

X-rays are detected via the product of their interactions (for example, emitted photoelectrons). The total X-ray detection efficiency is primarily determined by the product of 2 efficiency factors. The geometric efficiency (fill factor) refers to the efficient X-ray sensitive area of the detector and the quantum efficiency (capture efficiency) refers to the efficient absorbed photons that contribute to the output signal [13].

Flat Panel Detector

Figure 2.3: Composition of a digital flat-panel X-ray detector and Schematic illustration of the signal conversion chain inside the detector[13].

Figure 2.4: Schematic illustration of the flat detector field and a single detector element of the field [13]

A solid state flat panel detector as illustrated in Figure 2.3 is made up of sensor elements that include a photodiode and a thin-film transistor(TFT), which are made of amorphous silicon enclosed in a glass substrate. The pixel matrix is covered with cesium iodide layer (CsI).

The X-rays firstly come in contact with CsI scintillator layer (see Figure 2.4) of the detector, which converts them into visible light. The generated light photons are then directed to the next processing unit i.e. the amorphous silicon matrix. The photodiodes converts these photons into electric charges. These electric charges are integrated and stored in a detection element which acts like a capacitor. The TFT then forwards the electric charges to the ROC (Read-out Chip) through a data link. The signal amplification and analog-to-digital conversion processes are carried out in the chip itself [13].

Since the quality of the detector is highly dependent on the size of X-ray-sensitive detector area, the insensitive spaces between detector elements must be minimized (refer to Figure 2.4).

2.3 Electron Interactions with Matter

Electron Ionization

Electron ionization is inelastic in nature. When the energy of the incident electron is greater than the binding energy of the orbital electron, i.e. $E > E_b$, then orbital electron is ejected. This creates an "ion-pair" which refers to the negatively charged ejected electron and the positively charged atom. The ejected electrons sometimes have sufficient energy to further cause ionization. These electrons are called *delta rays* and the ionization they cause are referred to as *secondary ionization*.

Bremsstrahlung

Bremsstrahlung is an inelastic collision with the nucleus. When the primary electron slams into the nucleus of the atom of the material, the electron slows down and changes direction due to the Coulomb field of the atom and the kinetic energy of the electron is altered into photons of X-ray radiation. The X-rays generated by this principle constitutes a multi-energy X-rays i.e. It is made of many wavelengths. The continuous X-ray spectrum is caused due to bremsstrahlung and the spikes are associated with the characteristic X-ray of the target atom in the X-ray tube.

Multiple scattering

Apart from the inelastic collisions with the atomic electrons, particles passing through matter undergo repeated (multiple) elastic Coulomb scattering due to nuclei. such occurrence has a smaller probability. The mass of the nuclei is greater than the primary electron, therefore energy transfer is negligible but each scattering contributes adds random component's zig-zag pathway. After the incident beam passes through the material, the resulting beam shows divergence greater than the initial beam.

Figure 2.5: Effect of Multiple Coulomb Scattering [14].

2.4 X-ray Interactions with Matter

The interaction of photons depends on the energy of the incident photon, the density and the thickness of the target material. The interaction can either occur with the nucleus, orbital electron or the atom as a whole. The result of such interactions has two possibilities. The affected target will either absorb the photon completely or scatter it. If the target is an orbital electron, the occurrence of interactions can be grouped into 2 depending on the strength with which the electrons are bound (loose or tight). If the energy of the incident photon (E_o) is slightly larger or equal to the binding energy (E_{BE}) i.e $E_o \leq E_{BE}$ then Photoelectric effect and Rayleigh scattering occur. When $E_o \gg E_{BE}$ then interactions like Compton scattering and Pair production would occur. Pair production shall not be discussed since it occurs beyond the diagnostic energy range (1.02 MeV).

Rayleigh Scattering

In Rayleigh or elastic scattering the incident photon interacts with the total atom. The photon is scattered (re-emitted) in a different directions, but close to that of the incident photon as seen in Figure 2.6. Here the photon retains its original energy. No ionization and no loss of energy takes place. This type of scattering occurs at low energies (15 to 30 keV), but increases in probability with decreasing energy. Detection of a scattered photon has a negative effect on image quality, however the probability of such occurrence in the diagnostic range (20-70 keV) is relatively infrequent.

Figure 2.6: Illustration of Rayleigh scattering[15].

Photoelectric Effect

In photoelectric effect (PE) the interaction of the incident photon occurs with inner shell electron of the atom where the energy of the incident photon is completely absorbed by the electron. This results in a photoelectron (ejected photoelectron) with energy (E_e) which is given by

$$E_e = E_o - E_{BE} \tag{2.2}$$

The empty hole created by the ejected photoelectron is immediately filled with an electron from an outer orbital resulting in the emission of characteristic X-ray (or Auger electron) as seen in Figure 2.7. The energy of the characteristic X-ray emitted indicates the difference in binding energies of the electron orbitals in that atom.

$$\text{probability of photoelectric absorption} \propto Z^3/E^3 \tag{2.3}$$

This process predominates when lower energy photons interact with high Z materials, such as tungsten. Due to the absorption of the incident X-ray without scatter, maximum subject contrast arises with a PE interaction. At incident energies $< 50 \text{ keV}$ PE plays an important role in medical imaging, causing an amplification of differences in attenuation between tissues which results in improvement of image contrast quality.

Figure 2.7: Illustration of photoelectric effect [15]. The incident photon interacts with the inner shell, as a result a photoelectron is ejected and a hole is created (image on left). The empty hole is immediately filled with an electron from an outer orbital resulting in the emission of characteristic X-ray (image on right).

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Compton Scattering

Compton scattering (CS) or inelastic scattering is the most dominant interaction of X-rays with soft tissues in the diagnostic range and beyond (approx $30\text{ keV} - 30\text{ MeV}$). CS takes place when incident photon and a loosely bound outer shell electron of an atom interact. As a result the atom is ionized, the photon is scattered and an electron is ejected. The ejected (Compton) electron loses its energy via excitation and ionization. The original photon gets deflected or scattered at an angle θ , which in turn decreases the image contrast. Conservation of energy is given by

$$E_o = E_{sc} + E_e \quad (2.4)$$

At diagnostic energies (20-150 keV) most of the energy is transferred to the scattered photon. The energy of the scattered photon E_{sc} can be calculated from the energy of the incident photon E_o and the angle of the scattered photon θ . m_{ec}^2 is the electron mass energy with the following formula [16]:

$$E_{sc} = \frac{E_o}{1 + \left(\frac{E_o}{m_{ec}^2}\right) (1 - \cos \theta)} \quad (2.5)$$

Probability of Compton interaction increases with increase of incident photon energy and electron density. In tissue, the number of electrons per gram is fairly constant, therefore the probability is roughly proportional to material density.

Figure 2.8: Illustration of inelastic or Compton interaction [15].

2 Background

Total Attenuation

The reduction in intensity of the primary photons is referred to as attenuation. Attenuation depends on the type of material through which the X-ray passes. Linear attenuation coefficient μ , expresses the probability of removal of a photon from the X-ray beam per unit thickness of the material. The total attenuation, or linear attenuation coefficient for a given material, is expressed as the sum of each individual photon interaction.

$$\mu = \mu_{\text{Photoelectric}} + \mu_{\text{Compton}} + \mu_{\text{Rayleigh}} \quad (2.6)$$

The mean X-ray energy increases as it passes through an object being scanned. This phenomenon is known as beam hardening. This is because in a polychromatic beam like X-ray, the lower energy photons are attenuated more readily than high energy photons. Attenuation of X-rays depends on the thickness of the material and its absorption coefficient. A medical image is produced based on the concept of detection of photons transmitted through the material. This process is described by the Beer-Lambert law [17].

$$I_x = I_0 e^{-\mu x} \quad (2.7)$$

I_x is the beam intensity transmitted through the material of thickness x , I_0 is the original intensity, and μ is the linear attenuation coefficient.

Figure 2.9: Photon attenuation values for CsI [18]

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Monte Carlo Simulation

3.1.1 Overview of the Method

Monte Carlo (MC) simulations, are computer-aided mathematical techniques that rely on repeated random sampling to obtain numerical results. The underlying concept is to use randomness to solve problems that might be deterministic in principle. Whenever there is a chance of different outcomes in a particular process, which can not be easily predicted due to the presence of random variables, MC simulation can be implemented. However, in order to mimic any given system using MC method, 2 main components are required:

- A proper Random Number Generator (RNG)
- A good Probability Density Function (PDF)

With the use of random sampling and statistical models, MC simulations can help us define mathematical functions, which would enable us to imitate complicated systems [19] and thus be able to estimate its output. Basically a set of numerical methods are combined to create a stochastic MC algorithm. It uses random numbers to approximate solutions or to simulate different processes. Such algorithms help in delivering useful results.

It allows us to see, what results a particular course of action could produce and what is the likelihood of the occurrence of such results. When a random experiment is defined and event of interest is selected, the random experiment is executed many number of times. The RNG can highly influence the correctness of the estimator and the quality of the outcome [20].

Random Number Generation

A good source of a random number generation is the time between decays of radioactive elements [21] In reality, computer RNGs do not truly generate random numbers. For this reason, they are sometimes referred to pseudo-RNGs. RNGs mimic the behavior of true random numbers and are generated in a deterministic and predictable way.

There are a number of very good pseudo-RNGs available. To evaluate the correctness and effectiveness of these RNGS many tests have been developed, such as the RNG test suite of NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) [22] and the TestU01 [23].

The ideal RNG has the following characteristics [24]:

- The sequence of random numbers must be serially unrelated, the n-tuples of the sequence is required to be independent of eachother.
- While ideally it should not cycle at all, in practice, the repetition should occur only after generating huge set of numbers.
- The sequence should be uniform and unbiased, that is, equal fractions of generated numbers should fall into equal intervals.
- The algorithm of RNG and its implementation should be as efficient and as fast as possible.

To date, most RNGs are based on three types of methods: linear congruential generators (LCGs), lagged Fibonacci generators (LFGs) and the Mersenne Twister (MT) . Especially the Mersenne Twister presents an interesting alternative to standard RNGs, which are typically based on LCGs.

The linear congruential generator is a very simple example of a random number generator. Given the n^{th} sample, I_n , the next sample is

$$I_{n+1} = (aI_n + c) \text{ mod } m \tag{3.1}$$

where a, c, and m must be carefully chosen for best performance. However, LCG is an outdated generator that despite having best choice of these constants doesn't perform well on many tests like the TestU01 or similar tests. There was a need for an RNG that could overcome the limitations of previous RNGs.

Mersenne Twister: A RNG in MC Simulation

The name Mersene Twister is derived from the fact that it uses a period of $2^{19937} - 1$, which is a Mersenne prime. Mersenne prime is a prime number of the form $M_n = 2^n - 1$, for some integers of n . Examples of such values of n are 2,3,5,19,31 etc. The MT presents an interesting alternative to the standard RNGs. It was basically designed specifically to rectify most of the flaws found in older RNGs.

It is a well advanced RNG, which has widely become the generator of choice for general-purpose usage [25]. It is complicated but fast, it passes most randomness tests except for some that are for RNGs meant to be used in encryption. The source code for MT is freely available online .

Figure 3.1: Random points generated by Mersenne Twister[26]

Many of the well renowned software systems today adopt Mersenne Twister as a default RNG. some good examples are MATLAB [27], Excel [28], Python [29] etc.. The MC simulation in this thesis uses Mersenne Twister as RNG .

Probability Distribution function (PDF)

PDFs are the foundation of MC Simulations. They are functions that states the range of possible events and the relative probability of occurrence of these events for a given step in a simulation. A PDF should be a positive real-valued function, and its integral over the entire space is equal to 1. That is the sum of $p(x)$ for all possible values of x is 1, that is

$$\sum_j p_j = 1 \quad (3.2)$$

where j represents all possible values that x can have and P_j is the probability at x_j . For a uniform distribution with range from a to b , where $a < b$ are real numbers, the range in which x lies is given by,

$$a \leq x \leq b \quad (3.3)$$

and probability of x , ie $p(x)$ can be given as:

$$0 \leq p(x) \leq 1 \quad (3.4)$$

3.1.2 Estimating the value of Pi using Monte Carlo

The most fascinating number in mathematics is π (3.141592..). It is a constant meant to estimate the circumference of a circle from its radius or diameter. The peculiarity of this number is that it could be estimated to an infinite number of decimal places without undergoing a repeated pattern. Although this seems difficult to calculate, MC simulation can be used to estimate it.

In Figure 3.2, we have a circle of radius 0.5, enclosed by a 1x1 square. We know that area of the square is 1 unit sq while that of circle is

$$\pi * \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{\pi}{4} \quad (3.5)$$

For very huge number of randomly generated points the following formula can be used to estimate the value of π

$$\frac{\text{area of circle}}{\text{area of square}} = \frac{\text{no. of generated points inside the circle}}{\text{Total no.of generated points inside the square}} \quad (3.6)$$

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which implies,

$$\pi = 4 * \frac{\text{no. of points inside the circle}}{\text{Total no.of points inside the square}} \quad (3.7)$$

Points generated inside the circle are also part of the square, since the circle is included inside the square. Basically all the generated points are points in the square. The question is, how are points inside the circle differentiated from the ones outside the circle. Well, every time a point with random variables of x (0,1) and y (0,1) is generated, the computer calculates the distance (hypotenuse) of the point from the center of the circle using

$$d = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \quad (3.8)$$

If the distance d is less than or equal to the radius, then the point is said to be part of the circle.

In each of the figures Figure 3.2, Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4 [30] the value of π is estimated using equation Equation 3.7. It is quite clear how the increase in number of generated points brings us closer to estimate the value of π .

Figure 3.2: Low random point generation ($\pi=3.19072$)

Figure 3.3: Medium random point generation ($\pi=3.13604$)

Figure 3.4: High random point generation ($\pi=3.14468$)

This shows the importance of greater number of sample points to reach closer to the apt value of the actual result. Basically MC method utilizes an RNG to randomly generate numbers or events to mimic random processes and adapt them to the appropriate probability density functions to obtain results for complex systems.

In this case, random generation of points were simulated using Mersenne Twister with uniform distribution. The distribution type in case of simulation of physics processes is however non-uniform and complex in nature.

3.2 Geant4 (Geometry and Tracking)

3.2.1 Geant4 toolkit and its main domains

There are many general purpose Monte Carlo simulation Toolkits that model particle interaction with matter.

Monte Carlo based Softwares for particle tracking		
MC Code	Particle Types	Programming language
ERTAN	photons, electrons	Fortran
MCNP	Photons, electrons, neutrons	Fortran
MCNPX	all particles	Fortran
EGS4	photons, electrons	Fortran
EGSnrc	photons, electrons	Fortran
PENELOPE	photons, electrons	Fortran
Geant3	all particles	Fortran
Geant4	all particles	C++

Table 3.1: List of Monte Carlo software packages available for particle physics simulations

Of all the previous developed Fortran based MC softwares, Geant4 shows best flexibility in usage and has greater possibilities of expansion due to the object-oriented C++ programming language with which it is created.

With Geant4 it is possible to design experimental geometrical construction of different shapes and materials and to choose the particles and physics interactions to be involved in the experiment. The user can not only track the particle in matter but can also describe the response of a detector. Users are also provided with interfaces to enable them to interact with their simulation application and store the output. Visualisation drivers and graphical user interfaces are included in the Toolkit.

The key domains of the simulation in Geant4 are:

- Geometry and materials
- Particle interaction in matter
- Tracking management
- Digitisation and hit management
- Event and track management
- Visualisation and visualisation framework
- User interface.

Figure 3.5: Top Level Category Diagram of the Geant4 toolkit. The open circle on the joining lines represents a using relationship; the category at the circle end uses the adjoined category [31] Picture courtesy of Geant4 Collaboration.

Geometry and Materials: The design of a geometrical structure and description of the particles propagation in it is described by the geometry package. Geant4 follows a hierarchical geometrical set-up, let's say Box1 is inside Box2, this means Box2 is the mother of Box1. Box1 considered as daughter structure of Box2. All structures are set-up under a Box called World. Any given structure can be set with a material of choice this is taken care of by the material package. It replicates what exist in nature. Materials can be of single element or a mixture of elements. Likewise elements can be of single or a mixture of isotopes.

Particle source: Geant4's particle package gives the user a variety of particle choices to irradiate the experimental setup with. The type of primary particle, its energy, momentum, spatial and angular distribution can be modelled using simple interactive commands. For simple radiation field, a G4ParticleGun is used and for complex fields a GPS (General Particle Source) is recommended.

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Tracking component: The tracking of particles in an experimental-set up is the responsibility of the tracking package. A step is the distance between two interaction points and a track is a sequence of steps. The track constitutes information about the particle's position, kinetic energy, its energy deposition during a step and the physics interactions undertaken. Geant4 treats physics processes in a very generic way. Tracking independent on the particle type or on the specific physics process.

Event and run: The fundamental unit of the simulation in Geant4 is the event. It commences when a primary particle gets generated and stops after all the primary and secondary particles are completely tracked. A run on the other hand refers to collection of events that have common experimental conditions. During a run process, the geometrical set-up, detector design and the physics processes involved is not editable. Altering their configuration is possible either before or after the run.

Detector and hit management: The detection of a particle in the detector in terms of information such as energy deposition, particle momentum, time and position of interaction, is managed by the detector package. The information stored in the detector by an object called Hit. It is created in the sensitive detector. A hit is basically a storing version of the track information, at the point when the particle hits the sensitive detector. At the end of the *run* process, the hit collection is stored in the output file.

Interactivity and visualisation: The packages assigned for interface and visualizations are intercoms, interfaces, and visualisation. These packages provide the user the ability to visualise the geometrical structure of the experimental set-up and to track the particles in the experiment. The paths of the particles are coloured based on their charge. Positive charge (positrons) is designated as blue, negative charge (electrons) as red and neutral charge (photons) as green. Some graphical interfaces in Geant4 are Qt, OpenGL, Raytracer, ASCII Tree, GaGTree etc. Visualization of simulations with high number of primary particles is not recommended as it uses a lot of memory space. The execution of the simulation can therefore be done without enabling the visualization. The output of the simulation can be viewed using a software called ROOT once the execution of the simulation is completed.

3.2.2 Physics processes of particle-matter interaction

A particle in motion undergoes a number of physical processes in a medium, with cross sections which is dependent on the type of particle, its energy, and the properties of the medium. The particles often have to travel through different materials, shapes and sizes before it gets detected or decays completely.

As per Geant4, the particle in the experimental set-up progresses in a step by step fashion from the point of origin. A step is considered the distance between interaction points of the particle. At the beginning step, all physics processes of the particle propose the next possible interaction point by sampling their interaction lengths (aka Mean Free Path).

The medium target having density ρ made by i isotopes of mass m_i , fraction of x_i , the interaction length λ is estimated as follows [32]:

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\rho \sum_i \frac{x_i \sigma_i}{m_i}} \quad (3.9)$$

σ is the cross section of the specific process. The Mean Free Path (MFP) of a particle for a given process depends on the medium. In radiation physics, the probability of a particle to survive a distance dx can be given by:

$$P(x) = e^{-\frac{dx}{\lambda}} \quad (3.10)$$

the probability to survive along a path l is then:

$$P(l) = e^{-\int_0^l \frac{dx}{\lambda}} \quad (3.11)$$

where,

$$\int_0^l \frac{dx}{\lambda(x)} \quad (3.12)$$

is the no. of MFPs. Note that this physics quantity does not depend on the material being traversed nor on the particle energy. Now Equation 3.12 can be rewritten as

$$P(l) = e^{-n\lambda} \quad (3.13)$$

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i.e the probability distribution of n_λ is a simple exponential term independent of the material density and energy. n_λ can be used to sample interaction point. Therefore, we have

$$n_\lambda = -\ln \eta \quad (3.14)$$

η is a random number uniformly distributed in the range $(0, 1)$, and it is useful to measure the distance l to the point of interaction in the current material, for the specific process.

The interaction length is sampled for every process with distinct random numbers, producing a step. The tracking component examines all physics processes for the defined particle and choose which of them to initiate. The shortest interaction length decides the process to undertake unless a volume boundary of the experimental set-up is encountered in less than the sampled length. In such a case no physics interactions will occur and the particle is transported to the boundary of the designed geometry.

The interaction lengths of those processes which were not chosen, get their interaction lengths reduced due to the distance covered in the previous step, this given by the equation

$$n_\lambda^i = n_\lambda - \frac{\Delta x}{\lambda(x)} \quad (3.15)$$

This procedure [32] is repeated.

3.3 GATE (Geant4 Application for Tomographic Emission)

3.3.1 GATE overview

GATE is an opensource software developed by openGATE collaboration and is dedicated to simulations in medical imaging of Emission Tomography (PET and SPECT), CT, optical imaging (Bioluminescence and Fluorescence) and dose calculation in radiotherapy experiments.

The drawbacks of the already existing imaging simulation softwares, led to serious discussions for the need of development of a new toolkit dedicated to emission tomography. An object-oriented solution was preferred. In 2002, the first OpenGATE meeting took place in Lausanne(Switzerland), with first live demonstration of the first version of GATE. Since then many versions of it has been released [33] .

GATE is built based on Geant4 MC code and it uses Geant4 libraries for the simulation of particle transport. GATE simulations employs a Geant4 script language or macro language. Therefore, it does not require the user to have any prior C++ programming skills in order to carry out a GATE simulation [11]. In short, it combines the Geant4 toolkit including its physics models and complex geometry descriptions with powerful 3D visualization to simplify its use and promote research in the field of medical imaging.

Figure 3.6: Sketch of the layered architecture of GATE [11]

The program as seen in Figure 3.6 has a layered architecture. The Geant4 layer includes several hundreds of C++ classes. The core layer manages the process used to manage geometry, time and particle sources. Application layer implements the user classes obtained from the core layer to construct a specific geometrical shape and set its rotation

and translation. The user level is the outer most layer, where the simulation is set up using command based script.

The user interface

GATE uses an easy to use script language that helps the user to perform his simulation without having to face the complexity of computer programming. Macros have a .mac extension and are essentially ASCII files. Each command in a macro carries out a specific function. A function may require primary and secondary parameters. The Gate commands follow a tree structure, with respect to the function they present. For example, all commands that deal with shape of an object, are found under the /geometry/ branch of the tree. Commenting a command is done by adding the symbol '#'.

Usually these components are visualization, definitions of volumes (geometry), systems, digitizer, physics, initialization, source, output and start. These steps are described in the sections 1.4. A single simulation may be split into several macros, for instance one for the geometry, one for the physics, etc.

Gate simulations includes a master macro (main macro), which calls the more specific macros that deal with different components of the program. Splitting macros allows the user to re-use one or more of these macros in several other simulations and to organize the set of all commands. To execute a source macro from the main macro, the following command is used:

/control/execute source.mac

The components in a macro file must be placed in the correct order to carry out the simulation successfully. To understand the order of the components, one needs to have a look at Figure 3.13 Gate simulation architecture .

3.3.2 Particle flow management

Gate uses Geant4 to produce particles and transport them through materials. It imitates the particle's interaction in matter.

Step 1: Particle generation.

Each particle generated comes with its basic information like , its type, time of generation, momentum and energy.

Step 2: Application of an initial trajectory step.

A step represents the distance or the trajectory between 2 interaction points in a physical interaction (photoelectric effect, compton effect etc.).The length of a step varies depending on the nature of the physical interaction, particle type and material.

Step 3: If a step occurs inside the SD (Sensitive Detector). The interaction information between the particle and the material is stored.

This set of information that includes the deposited energy, the momentum before and after the interaction, the name of the volume where the interaction occurred, etc. is called a *Hit*.

Step 4: Repetition of step 2 and 3.

Repetition is performed till energy of particle is reduced in comparison to its actual defined value. The entire series of steps beginning with generation of the particle to its detection at the detector is referred to as a *Track*.

Step 5: The digitization step filters the energy deposited in a crystal.

Output received after the processing of the digitizer module corresponds to a signal. The digitizer performs the work of a Front End Electronics (FEE). This process of transforming the energy of a *Hit* into the final digital value is called *Digitization* and is performed by the GATE digitizer as seen in Figure 3.7. The final output received at the end of the digitizer module is called a *Single*. For information regarding the digitizer refer to section 3.4.2.

Figure 3.7: The digitizer is organized as a chain of modules that begins with the hit and ends with the single which represents the physical observable seen from the detector.

3.3.3 Variance Reduction Technique

Variance reduction techniques are often employed in MC simulations to increase the efficiency ϵ , which can be defined as:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{T \cdot \sigma^2}$$

where T time required to perform the simulation and σ is the variance. Given a certain time T to perform a simulation, what is the smallest variance we can obtain, which corresponds to increase the efficiency of the simulation.

There are many VRTs in Gate to accelerate the simulation process. some good examples of Gate VRTs are, the regular navigator and the fictitious interaction approach designed mainly for SPECT and PET [34], the tabulated modelling of detector response in SPECT which avoids the tracking of particles within collimator-detector pair [35] and the strategic method of voxel compression to enhance memory and CPU usage [36].

CT simulation in Gate applies population control method as a VRT technique. Methods such as particle splitting and Russian roulette belong to this category. These methods control the quantities of particles to be sampled based on their importance.

Figure 3.8: Illustration of avoiding the tracking of particles that are of no use for the simulation to accelerate the execution process

Efficiency increase of CT simulations is achievable by splitting every photon that reaches the detector area into k clones. Each clone formed by the photon split, interacts with the detector using direct inversion method. Normally $k = 1$ (without splitting of particles).

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Considering N to be the number of photons hitting the detector surface and p the detection probability, then the number of detected photons would follow a Poisson's distribution of mean and variance equal to Np . For this to happen, a large value of N and a small value of p is required [37]. Taking into consideration the use of k clones, the number of detected photons would be Nkp and its variance would be given by

$$(Nkp)^2[(k-1)/Nk + 1/Nkp] \quad (3.16)$$

Figure 3.9: Plot of the relative variance against mean photons/pixel (a) and simulation time (b) [37]

As shown in Figure 3.9(a), the relative variance that is obtained on account of the acceleration option is well described. There is rapid increase in the relative variance when k becomes large. Figure 3.9(b) describes the accelerations reached using the splitting method. 10 clones of the photon, i.e. $k = 10$ results in decrease of execution time by 10 with little change of relative variance. Using $k = 20$ which is 20 clones of the photon, would affect the relative variance dramatically.

This method is very beneficial for improving the execution time but the user is advised to cautiously use higher values of k , as the increase of relative variance might lead to reconstructed images with noise.

3.3.4 Cluster computing using Gate-Lab

VRT can not only reduce variance but can also accelerate the GATE simulation to certain extent. However, the acceleration attained using VRT is incomparable to the GATE simulation's processing speed attained through use of cluster computing. Cluster computing consists of set of connected computers that work together to complete a certain computational task. It provides much faster processing speed, larger storage capacity and better data integrity. Cluster computing has been successfully implemented in other MC packages. Significant works on parallelization of MC N-Particle (MCNP) [38] and an incredible speed increase factor that approached the number of processors using Message Passing Interface (MPI) [39] was reported. In order to reduce the overall computing time of the GATE experiments, a parallel computing platform GATE-Lab was used for running the MC simulation in cluster of computers on the EGI (European Grid Infrastructure).

The European Grid Infrastructure (EGI) is currently the largest production grid worldwide providing more than 100,000 CPUs and several Petabytes of storage. It uses the gLite middleware, which provides high level services for scheduling and running computational jobs, as well as for data and grid infrastructure management. A User Interface (UI) is the initial point of access to the grid from which the user can be authenticated and authorized to use the grid resources. From the UI the user can submit and cancel jobs, query their status and retrieve their output. These tasks are taken into account by a Workload Management System (WMS), which queues the user requests and dispatches them to the different computing centres available. (i) the client which consists in the VIP (Virtual Imaging Platform) offering a GUI for grid data management, (ii) a lab server managing task submission, monitoring and error handling and (iii) the grid itself, externally administrated and accessible through gLite.

GATE-Lab allows for preparing a new simulation and launching it on the grid. The end user is asked for a name of the new simulation, constituent macros and for its main macro file. The client checks the simulation parameters, looks for all local input files, bundles them into an archive and uploads it to the grid. The parallelized simulations are made up of 3 steps: the job distribution, the actual simulations (on a number of CPUs) and file merging.

The number of parallel tasks (job splitting) to submit to the grid is automatically determined based on the end user estimation of the total CPU time needed for the complete simulation. The total CPU time depends on the number of events, but also on their type. At the moment, the mapping corresponds to a minimum of 5 jobs for short simulations

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Figure 3.10: Schematic overview of the job splitter

(a few minutes) and goes to a maximum of 500 jobs for simulations lasting more than a day. The information of the split file, generated by the job splitter (Figure 3.10), is used to merge the ROOT files into a single output file. The last eventID of each subsimulation as an offset for the next subsimulation. The output file merger is responsible for a large amount of the total computation time. This is mainly due to the large data transfers from hard drive to memory and vice versa while merging the output data into a single file with correct eventIDs.

Figure 3.11: Schematic overview of the novel merging approach

3.3.5 Output Formats

Gate has several types of output formats for its users. There is default output format enabled in Gate, the user has to enable it since by default all the available formats are disabled. To enable any output the following command is used.

```
/gate/output/"output – type"/enable
```

The output types in Gate are ROOT, ASCII(binary), Interfile (can be read with ImageJ and IDL), Sinogram, Ecat7, LMF and Image CT output.

ASCII binary output allows the user to process the data with the user's own tools. One of the problems of ASCII output is that it is not compressed. They produce large files. It is therefore recommended not to enable ASCII, in order to speed up the simulation and save memory space.

ROOT [40] is a data analysis tool kit. It provides all the functionalities needed to deal with big data processing, statistical analysis, visualisation and storage. Using ROOT's TBrowser, a user can type-in the following command to visualize the graph of any 2 given variables

```
Singles>-Draw("variable1:variable2")
```

In ASCII the parameter data is properly ordered, which makes it possible for a user to view only the parameters he/she is interested in. Parameters are arranged in the order of runID, EventID, SourceID, SourceX, SourceY, SourceZ, time, energy, globalPosX, globalPoxY, globalPoxZ, IDgantary, ModuleID, pixelID, clusterID etc.(please note that parameters from IDgantry to clusterID are counted as 1 parameter. One can either enable them all or disable them all). By default all parameters are enabeled. In case if a user is interested only in the X and Y of the global position of Singles in the sensitive Detector. The following command can be used

```
/gate/output/ascii/setSingleMask0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0
```

The ImageCT output is a binary matrix of float numbers that stores the simulated CT image and is produced for each time slice. The output file name is "test_XXX.dat", where XXX is the corresponding time slice number. The imageCT output can be read in Matlab to reconstruct the image and perform any other available processing procedures.

3.4 Experimental Design

3.4.1 CBCT setup and measurements

The Monte Carlo CT simulation using Gate in this thesis attempts to mimic the CT configuration from Artis zeego (Siemens Healthineers, Forchheim, Germany).

The availability of this CT scanner in the medical university hospital campus (Mannheim), in CUBEX41 medical technology development center to be precise, makes it convenient to access the CT device from the department of computer assisted clinical medicine, which is located within the hospital itself.

A water container as seen in Figure 3.12 was used as a phantom to obtain CT measurements with which the simulation results will be validated with. The phantom had to be simple in structure in order to generate a copy of it in Gate. It was positioned in the iso center with help of the x and y laser planes.

The maximum high energy voltage applied across the x-ray tube (Peak Kilovoltage) is 70keV. It uses a 2.5mm thick aluminium material as a filter and has an anode angle of 12° . Artis zeego CT uses a flat detector of dimension $30 \times 38cm$ and comprises of $2480 \times 1920pixels$ each of size $154\mu m$. It is positioned at a distance of $1.2m$ and $0.4m$ from the source and the iso center respectively.

The CT simulation specifications and design in this thesis is based on design parameters obtained from Artis zeego Data sheet [41] and DICOM tags of the CT image obtained from Zeego scanner.

parameters used for the GATE simulation	
Parameters	Value
Peak Kilo Voltage (PKV) of X-ray	70 <i>keV</i>
Anode angle	12°
Thickness of Aluminium (filter)	2.5 <i>mm</i>
Active Imaging Size	382 <i>mm</i> \times 296 <i>mm</i>
Pixel size	154 μm
Image display matrix	2480 \times 1920 <i>pixels</i>
Source to detector distance	1197 <i>mm</i>
Source to patient distance	785 <i>mm</i>
patient to detector distance	413 <i>mm</i>

Table 3.2: List of parameters from Zeego Artis used for the CT Simulation

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Figure 3.12: Illustration of rotation of the Zeego Artis CT and its corresponding phantom rotation in Gate at 0° , 45° and 90°

3.4.2 CBCT simulation with GATE

For the simulation in this thesis, the latest available version of Gate was installed: vGate version 8.2 and Ubuntu LTS version 18.04.

Due to the cumbersome nature of the GATE software. A vGATE or better called a virtual GATE machine that is developed using the freely available Virtual Box software was introduced to avoid complexity during the installation of the software. vGATE contains all the necessary softwares (Ubuntu with Virtual Box, GATE, GateContrib, Geant4, ITK, VTK, vV, ImageJ, Jupyter Notebook, Python3) compatible with each other. vGATE helps to launch a GATE simulation in just few steps and it can be hosted on any operating system such as Linux, Windows, MacOS etc..

Simulation architecture for CT imaging in Gate

The experiment is carried on step by step depending on the order in which different macros are to be executed according to Gate. To run the simulation successfully the macros are supposed to be arranged in a specific manner within the main macro. This arrangement can be seen in Figure 3.13

Figure 3.13: Gate simulation architecture

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Main Macro: After having all the sub-macros ready to be executed, they are called from the main macro to execute the simulation.

```
# VISUALIZATION #  
/control/execute mac/visu.mac  
  
# SET MATERIAL DATABASE #  
/gate/geometry/setMaterialDatabase data/GateMaterials.db  
  
# WORLD DISCRPTION #  
/control/execute mac/world.mac  
  
# PHANTOM #  
/control/execute mac/Watercylinder.mac  
  
# SCANNER #  
/control/execute mac/scanner.mac  
  
# COLLIMATOR #  
/control/execute mac/collimator.mac  
  
# PHYSICS #  
/control/execute mac/physics.mac  
  
# INITIALIZATION #  
/gate/run/initialize  
  
# DIGITIZER #  
/control/execute mac/digitizer.mac  
  
# SOURCE #  
/control/execute mac/source.mac  
  
# OUTPUT #  
/control/execute mac/output.mac  
  
# RANDOMNESS GENERATOR #  
/control/execute mac/Random-generator.mac  
  
# NUMBER OF PHOTONS#  
/gate/application/setTotalNumberOfPrimaries 4000000  
  
# This is the command to launch the simulation#  
/gate/application/start
```

Visualization Parameters

Gate enables the user to visualize the outcome of the written script code. There are various graphics systems that are supported by Gate. For example Raytracer, Qt and OpenGL. Using these softwares the user is able to view particle trajectories, tracking steps, detector components, phantom and other similar structures.

If the user would like to have the User Interface and all Visualization windows in the same window then Qt is recommended. The user can zoom ,rotate and translate objects in Qt without having to insert extra script codes in it. Another important useful tool in Qt is that it is provided with video-making feature, where by the user can record the video of the graphic interface and store it as a video.

If no editing is to be done, it is advised to use OpenGL, since it has a very fast response compared to other graphic softwares.

Script commands for Visualization.mac

```
/vis/open OGL  
/vis/reviewKeptEvents  
/vis/viewer/set/viewpointThetaPhi 45  
/vis/viewer/zoom 5  
/vis/drawVolume  
/tracking/storeTrajectory 0  
/vis/scene/add/trajectories  
/vis/scene/endOfEventAction accumulate -1  
/vis/scene/add/axes  
/vis/viewer/update
```

Material composition

The default material assigned to a new volume is Air. The list of available materials is defined in the GateMaterials.db file. The location of the material database needs to be specified with the following command:

```
/gate/geometry/setMaterialDatabase MyMaterialDatabase.db
```

Not all materials can be found in the database. However, the user can add a material of choice to the material database (MyMaterialDatabase.db) if the composition of its elements and its density is known. A new material, CsI (Cesium Iodide) was added for the detector by providing the below mentioned data in the material database.

```
CsI : d = 4.51g/cm3; n = 2  
+ el : name = Cesium; f = 0.51155  
+ el : name = Iodine; f = 0.48845
```

The following information about the elements of the CsI material, Cesium and Iodine is found in the database.

```
Iodine : S = I; Z = 53.; A = 126.90g/mole  
Cesium : S = Cs; Z = 55.; A = 132.905g/mole
```

Where d is the density of the material, n is the number of atoms in the compound and f refers to the fraction of element in the compound. Z is the atomic number and A is the atomic weight of the element. The letter S refers to the symbol of the element.

Before mentioning any material in the macro, the user have to make sure that the material database is called using the above given command, else an error will pop up which would hinder the progress to run the simulation. Another important thing to note is the correct mentioning of the material. Since the materials are saved in the database as 'Water' or 'Air', referring to these materials as 'water' or 'air' (lowercase) would make it difficult for the system to recognize it.

World definition

The first volume is the world, which is already existent by default. It has a geometry of a box. All secondary volumes used in the simulation are contained inside the world. It is similar to a room where the imaging CT device is located. It is centered at the origin (the iso center). It can be of any size and has to be large enough to include the entire simulation geometry. The tracking of any particle stops when it escapes from the world volume.

The user can directly add the dimensions of the World box without having to create the volume, since the World box volume is present in Gate by default. Geometry dimensions, material and colour of the volume can be specified.

Script commands for World.mac

```
/gate/world/geometry/setXLength 4. m  
/gate/world/geometry/setYLength 4. m  
/gate/world/geometry/setZLength 4. m  
/gate/world/setMaterial Air  
/gate/world/vis/forceWireframe  
/gate/world/vis/setColor white
```


Figure 3.14: World volume [42]

Definition of the phantom geometry

Gate provides the user the flexibility to design 3D phantoms of different shapes and sizes. Using the available material database, the phantoms can be made of various materials too.

During the course of the experiment with Gate, various phantoms have been created and used. To understand the concept of 3D imaging a simple phantom made of Air cylinder, containing 2 different sized spheres (yellow and white) made of Aluminium was created as shown in Figure 3.15. Projection of photons from a static source while rotating the phantom can give us a 3D image by adapting the image reconstruction process.

Figure 3.15: Illustration of the phantom with 2 aluminum spheres viewed from different angles

Another simple phantom developed is the 4 cylinder AWBAT phantom. It was designed for understanding the x-ray interaction with different body tissues. It has one big water cylinder and 3 other cylinders (made of bone, aluminium and titanium) placed within the water cylinder as seen in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16: Illustration of the AWBAT phantom of water cylinder containing bone (red), aluminium (light brown) and titanium(dark brown).

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The XCAT phantom [43] provides a rich library of human body anatomies. For example, adult, child, male, female, obese, non-obese anatomies etc, user can also include tumors in the phantom. Gate permits the usage of this phantom. We shall use the 4D cardio-torso region of the XCAT phantom in this thesis. The XCAT phantom was read in the simulation in the '.mhd' format.

```
/gate/patient/geometry/setImage data/patient-2mm.mhd
```

For conversion of the HU(Hounsfield Unit) with which the phantom material is described to material. An HU to material conversion file is required (For conversion formula refer section 2.1, Equation 2.1). This is called from the .mac file using the command

```
/gate/geometry/setMaterialDatabase data/patient-HUmaterials.db
```


Figure 3.17: Illustration of the 4D cardio-torso (XCAT) phantom.

For validation with real data, a phantom that mimics the real plastic container filled with water was developed using Gate. Here, no table was constructed to hold the water container as in real case measurements (refer to Figure 3.12). However, it is positioned in the iso center. The measurements of the outer plastic cylinder and the inner water cylinder is given in Table 3.3.

parameters	Plastic cylinder	Water cylinder
Inner radius	56mm	0mm
Outer radius	58.86mm	56mm
height	137.77mm	137.77mm

Table 3.3: Geometrical measurements of the water container

Script commands for phantom.mac

```
# Plastic cylinder
```

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Figure 3.18: Illustration of the original water container phantoms and its replica in GATE.

```
/gate/world/daughters/name plasticCylinder
/gate/world/daughters/insert cylinder
/gate/plasticCylinder/geometry/setRmin 56. mm
/gate/plasticCylinder/geometry/setRmax 58.86 mm
/gate/plasticCylinder/geometry/setHeight 137.77 mm
/gate/plasticCylinder/setMaterial Plastic
/gate/plasticCylinder/vis/setColor cyan
/gate/plasticCylinder/vis/forceSolid
/gate/plasticCylinder/vis/setVisible true
```

Note: By default the geometries are placed in the iso center.

```
# Water cylinder
/gate/plasticCylinder/daughters/name waterCylinder
/gate/plasticCylinder/daughters/insert cylinder
/gate/waterCylinder/geometry/setRmin 0. mm
/gate/waterCylinder/geometry/setRmax 56. mm
/gate/waterCylinder/geometry/setHeight 137.77 mm
/gate/waterCylinder/setMaterial Water
/gate/waterCylinder/vis/setColor white
/gate/waterCylinder/vis/forceSolid
/gate/waterCylinder/vis/setVisible true
```

Now, the plastic and the water cylinder are attached to the phantom sensitive detector. The commands will inform Gate that the user is interested in the history of particles that interact in these volumes .

```
/gate/plasticCylinder/attachPhantomSD
/gate/waterCylinder/attachPhantomSD
```

Scanner definition

Modelling of the CT scanner was done using the *CTscanner* system as seen in Figure 3.19. The CT system comprises of components that can be replicated along a desired axis. A *module* is made up of clusters. The clusters include equally sized pixels. Such an arrangement gives the user flexibility to model different types of CT scanners.

Figure 3.19: Basic components of the *CTscanner* system in *Gate* [37].

The scanner design as per specifications from Table 3.2 with x and y dimensions of 382mm and 296mm respectively. The thickness (z axis) of the scintillator material (CsI) was estimated from [44]. The scanner's image display matrix is given as $2480 \times 1920\text{pixels}$ and it is positioned in the negative z axis at -412mm from the iso center. The pixel size is defined as $0.154 \times 0.154\text{mm}$.

script commands for Scanner.mac

Name, shape and dimensions of the scanner is defined. The material is set as Air and the outline of the *CTscanner* is visualized as a white wire frame. The scanner is placed at -412mm away from the source in the z axis.

```
# CTSCANNER #
/gate/world/daughters/name CTscanner
/gate/world/daughters/insert box
/gate/CTscanner/geometry/setXLength 382.00 mm
/gate/CTscanner/geometry/setYLength 296.00 mm
/gate/CTscanner/geometry/setZLength 0.5 mm
/gate/CTscanner/setMaterial Air
/gate/CTscanner/vis/forceWireframe
/gate/CTscanner/vis/setColor white
/gate/CTscanner/placement/setTranslation 0. 0. -412. mm
```

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The first component of the *CTscanner* system is the module, since only one module is used, it is created identical to the encompassing volume (*CTscanner*)

```
# CTSCANNER # -> # MODULE #  
/gate/CTscanner/daughters/name module  
/gate/CTscanner/daughters/insert box  
/gate/module/geometry/setXLength 382.00 mm  
/gate/module/geometry/setYLength 296.00 mm  
/gate/module/geometry/setZLength 0.5 mm  
/gate/module/setMaterial Air  
/gate/module/vis/forceWireframe  
/gate/module/vis/setColor white
```

The second component of the *CTscanner* system is the cluster (located inside the module). Since only one cluster is being used, it is created identical to the mother volume (the Module).

```
# CTSCANNER # -> # MODULE # -> # CLUSTER_0 #  
/gate/module/daughters/name cluster  
/gate/module/daughters/insert box  
/gate/cluster/geometry/setXLength 382.00 mm  
/gate/cluster/geometry/setYLength 296.00 mm  
/gate/cluster/geometry/setZLength 0.5 mm  
/gate/cluster/setMaterial Air  
/gate/cluster/vis/forceWireframe  
/gate/cluster/vis/setColor white
```

The third component of the *CTscanner* system is the pixel (located inside the cluster).

```
# CTSCANNER # -> # MODULE # -> # CLUSTER_0 # -> # PIXEL#  
/gate/cluster/daughters/name pixel  
/gate/cluster/daughters/insert box  
/gate/pixel/geometry/setXLength 0.154 mm  
/gate/pixel/geometry/setYLength 0.154 mm  
/gate/pixel/geometry/setZLength 0.5 mm  
/gate/pixel/setMaterial CsI  
/gate/pixel/vis/forceSolid  
/gate/pixel/vis/setColor red
```

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Now we can repeat the pixel inside the cluster, We want 2480×1920 pixels, each of size 0.154×0.154 mm. This is done as follows:

```
/gate/pixel/repeaters/insert cubicArray  
/gate/pixel/cubicArray/setRepeatNumberX 2480  
/gate/pixel/cubicArray/setRepeatNumberY 1920  
/gate/pixel/cubicArray/setRepeatNumberZ 1  
/gate/pixel/cubicArray/setRepeatVector 0.154 0.154 0. mm
```

The following commands allow GATE to make a link between the arbitrary volumes that are defined and the predefined components of the system in use (here the *CTscanner*). It makes a link with the output modules associated to the system.

```
/gate/systems/CTscanner/module/attach module  
/gate/systems/CTscanner/cluster_0/attach cluster  
/gate/systems/CTscanner/pixel_0/attach pixel
```

Attach the pixel as the crystal sensitive detector. This command is used to specify which arbitrary volume is used as the sensitive volume. All interactions occurring in this volume can be recorded and analyzed.

```
/gate/pixel/attachCrystalSD
```


Figure 3.20: Illustration of the CT scanner produced using Gate

Collimator design

Unfortunately Gate does not include the option of having a rectangular shaped beam, For this reason it was necessary to design a collimator to obtain this type of beam geometry. The collimator is made up of rectangular lead material of size $30 \times 30\text{cm}$ and a thickness of 0.5mm [45] with a 3D trapezoidal air opening in its center through which the photons reach the detector region (see Figure 3.24).

As seen in Figure 3.21, the inner and the outer rectangles of the trapezoid can be calculated using the intercept theorem. AC and $A'C'$ (y axis lengths) of box1 and box2 can be calculated as

$$AC = \frac{SC \times BD}{SD}, \quad A'C' = \frac{SC' \times BD}{SD}$$

Similarly the x axis lengths is given by

$$AF = \frac{SF \times BE}{SB}, \quad A'F' = \frac{SF' \times BE}{SB}$$

Figure 3.21: Design illustration to create a trapezoidal opening within the lead collimator to allow only important photons.

Figure 3.22: Illustration of the trapezoidal opening cut open from the lead collimator through which photons reach the detector

Script commands for collimator.mac

```
/gate/world/daughters/name trapi  
/gate/world/daughters/insert box  
/gate/trapi/geometry/setXLength 30. cm  
/gate/trapi/geometry/setYLength 30. cm  
/gate/trapi/geometry/setZLength 5. mm  
/gate/trapi/placement/setTranslation 0. 0. 720.0 mm  
/gate/trapi/setMaterial Lead  
/gate/trapi/vis/forceSolid  
/gate/trapi/vis/setColor red  
/gate/trapi/vis/setVisible true  
/gate/trapi/daughters/name trapeze  
/gate/trapi/daughters/insert trpd
```

the following commands are based on the calculations stated above for a trapezoidal collimator of thickness 5mm

```
/gate/trapeze/geometry/setX1Length 21.536 mm  
/gate/trapeze/geometry/setY1Length 16.673 mm
```

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```
/gate/trapeze/geometry/setX2Length 19.94 mm  
/gate/trapeze/geometry/setY2Length 15.438 mm  
/gate/trapeze/geometry/setZLength 5. mm  
/gate/trapeze/setMaterial Air  
/gate/trapeze/vis/forceSolid  
/gate/trapeze/vis/setColor grey  
/gate/trapeze/vis/setVisible true
```

Set up of the physics process

In the physics macro, the physical interactions that suit the interaction processes that take place in the attenuation and energy deposition of electrons/photons in matter in the respective energy window, like Bremsstrahlung, Electron Ionization, Multiple scattering, Compton Effect, Photoelectric Effect, Rayleigh Scattering are enabled.

In general, X-ray energy for diagnostic CT imaging is below 150keV [46], since pair production can't occur for X-ray photons below 1022keV , pair production is not considered in the simulation process.

All physics processes have 3 different possible states. They are *available*, *enabled* and *initialized*. By default the physics processes are all *available*. To be able to *initialize* these processes, the list of processes that are meaningful to this simulation is first selected using `addProcess` command. Then they are enabled and initialized using `processList Enabled` and `processList Initialized` commands respectively.

Script commands for physics.mac

```
/gate/physics/addProcess PhotoElectric
/gate/physics/processes/PhotoElectric/setModel StandardModel
/gate/physics/addProcess Compton
/gate/physics/processes/Compton/setModel PenelopeModel
/gate/physics/addProcess RayleighScattering
/gate/physics/processes/RayleighScattering/setModel PenelopeModel
/gate/physics/addProcess ElectronIonisation e-
/gate/physics/processes/ElectronIonisation/setModel StandardModel e-
/gate/physics/addProcess Bremsstrahlung e-
/gate/physics/processes/Bremsstrahlung/setModel StandardModel e-
/gate/physics/addProcess MultipleScattering e-
/gate/physics/processList Enabled
/gate/physics/processList Initialized
```

Initialization

It is a mandatory step that is meant to be executed after the geometrical volumes and the physics processes, but before source and Output.

```
/gate/run/initialize
```

Source definition

The X-ray source used is a GPS (General Particle Source) and the particles are defined as gamma particles. The source is positioned at 1197mm away from the detector and at 785mm from the iso center. The photon beam is directed towards the iso center where the phantom is placed. Data of the energy histogram for the X-ray energy range $10 - 70\text{keV}$ obtained for Aluminium filter of thickness 2.5mm and anode angle 12° was extracted from the SpeKCalc software [47] and used in the source macro file.

Script commands for source.mac

```
/gate/source/addSource xraygun
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/verbose 0
# Particle type
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/particle gamma
# Source position
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/centre 00. 00. 785. mm
# Cone beam angle
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/mintheta 0. deg
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/maxtheta 12. deg
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/angtype iso
# Source geometry
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/type Plane
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/shape Rectangle
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/halfx 0.025 mm
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/halfy 0.025 mm
# Energy distribution
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/energytype Arb
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histname arb
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.010 0.4125802
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.011 16.39023
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.012 280.0572
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.013 2281.61
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.014 11754.3
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.015 40323.54
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.016 105192.2
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.017 219277
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.018 386832.3
```

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/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.019 608615.8
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.020 870982.3
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.021 1.16E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.022 1.45E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.023 1.74E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.024 2.01E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.025 2.23E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.026 2.45E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.027 2.62E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.028 2.76E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.029 2.87E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.030 2.94E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.031 2.99E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.032 3.02E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.033 3.03E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.034 3.02E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.035 2.98E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.036 2.94E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.037 2.89E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.038 2.83E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.039 2.75E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.040 2.68E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.041 2.60E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.042 2.52E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.043 2.43E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.044 2.34E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.045 2.25E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.046 2.16E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.047 2.07E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.048 1.98E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.049 1.89E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.050 1.80E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.051 1.72E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.052 1.63E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.053 1.54E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.054 1.46E+06
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.055 1.37E+06

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```
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.056 1.29E+06  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.057 1.20E+06  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.058 1.12E+06  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.059 1.04E+06  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.060 960267.6  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.061 880274.3  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.062 800590.5  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.063 720090.4  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.064 639612.5  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.065 557725.7  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.066 474999.1  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.067 384103.9  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.068 296962.2  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.069 174495.8  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/histpoint 0.070 0  
/gate/source/xraygun/gps/arbint Lin  
/gate/source/list
```


Figure 3.23: Illustration of the cone beam produced by the GPS (before collimation).

Figure 3.24: Illustration of the rectangular shaped collimated beam (after collimation).

Definition of digitizer parameters

The digitizer module mimics the signal processing and detector behaviour. The obtained information is used to simulate the detector pulse (digits), which corresponds to observed data. The digitizer module in this thesis consists of sequence of 3 components, namely Adder, Readout and threshold.

Adder: The function of an adder is similar to that of the integrator in electronics. It sums all *hits* (hits can be compared to the input quantities of of an integrator) that occur within the same crystal (i.e. same volume). The adder groups the *hits* per volume into a *pulse*. If a particle enters a detector and makes 2 *hits* in 2 different crystals, the output of the adder will have 2 pulses but the energy considered will be the total of energies in each volume.

Readout: The readout has an artificial geometry that is associated with group of detectors. This is quite different from the usual detector system where every crystal is read by a single photo-detector. It basically regroups pulses per block (group of sensitive detectors). The resulted pulse has a total energy of all pulses summed together in that block.

Threshold: This module allows the user to specify the low energy cut and the high energy cut. Photons of energies below low energy mark and higher than the high energy mark are not taken into consideration since the user is not interested in them.

script commands for digitizer.mac

Adder

```
/gate/digitizer/Singles/insert adder
```

Readout

```
/gate/digitizer/Singles/insert readout
```

```
/gate/digitizer/Singles/readout/setDepth 2
```

Threshold

```
/gate/digitizer/Singles/insert thresholder
```

```
/gate/digitizer/Singles/thresholder/setThreshold 20 keV
```

```
/gate/digitizer/verbose 0
```

Data Output

In this thesis mainly 2 output formats are used, they are ROOT and Image CT. For more information about these outputs refer to subsection 3.3.5

script commands for output.mac

By default, all outputs are disabled, so the output formats should be first enabled. Since *singles* are useful to us, it is set to 1 (enable) and the rest are set to 0.

ROOT output

```
/gate/output/root/enable  
/gate/output/root/setFileName output/sample-test  
/gate/output/root/setRootHitFlag 0  
/gate/output/root/setRootSinglesFlag 1  
/gate/output/root/setRootNtupleFlag 0  
/gate/output/verbose 1
```

In order to visualize the outputs at every step within the digitizer the following commands are used

```
#/gate/output/root/setRootSinglesAdderFlag 1  
#/gate/output/root/setRootSinglesReadoutFlag 1  
#/gate/output/root/setRootSinglesThresholdFlag 1  
#/gate/output/root/setOutFileSinglesUpholderFlag 1
```

Image CT output

```
/gate/output/imageCT/enable  
/gate/output/imageCT/setFileName output/sample-test  
/gate/output/imageCT/verbose 0
```

Definition of the VRT, RNG and photon number

VRT (refer to subsection 3.3.3) for CT (the random seed is proper to the VRT module).

```
#/gate/output/imageCT/vrtFactor 10
```

```
#/gate/output/imageCT/setStartSeed 567489
```

selection of the RNG type as MersenneTwister

```
/gate/random/setEngineName MersenneTwister
```

```
/gate/random/verbose 1
```

defining the photon number

```
/gate/application/setTotalNumberOfPrimaries 4000000
```

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Simulation results

Overview of simulation results

GATE simulation results			
Nr.	Phantom	Simulation description	Result
1	AWBAT(Figure 3.16)	Sanity check. Result obtained using ROOT. Four million X-ray photons used. Kilovoltage peak = 70KeV	Figure 4.1
2	water cylinder (Figure 3.18)	Sanity check. Result obtained using ROOT. Three million X-ray photons used. Kilovoltage peak = 70KeV	Figure 4.2
3	XCAT (Figure 3.17)	Gate-lab computer cluster simulations performed with only one projection. 500 billion X-ray photons were used for a single projection. Kilovoltage peak = 120KeV	Figure 4.3
4	Water cylinder (Figure 3.18)	Gate-lab computer cluster simulation performed using a total of 500 billion X-ray photons for 100 projections. One projection for every 3.6° rotation taken. Kilovoltage peak = 70KeV	Figure 4.5

Table 4.1: Overview of GATE simulation results using phantoms in section 3.4.2

The result shown in this section are classified into sanity simulation results and actual results. The sanity simulations are quick simulations carried out using low number of photons meant to validate or check if the development progress of the GATE simulation is being created in a correct manner. The second type of simulations are the actual simulations carried out using much higher number of X-ray photons which are executed with the help of Gate-lab cluster computing platform. Using Gate-lab the simulations that are supposed to take weeks for completion was reduced to just 3 days. The first two

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simulations in Table 4.1 are sanity check descriptions whose results are obtained using ROOT software, while the third and fourth simulations are actual Gate-lab simulations. The raw data results obtained from cluster computation were loaded to a Matlab image reconstruction algorithm through which the raw data was processed and interpreted into a meaningful image.

Each dot in a ROOT image represents a hit and every white dot represents no hit on the detector. Depending upon the hit counts in the ROOT image the user can differentiate the materials in the image. Two ROOT images are shown here, Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2

ROOT results of AWBAT phantom

Figure 4.1: ROOT simulation results of the AWBAT phantom made of water, bone, aluminium and titanium.

ROOT results (section 3.4.2) of the AWBAT phantom (section 3.4.2, Figure 3.16) shows clear distinction between five different materials (Air, Water, Bone, Aluminium and Titanium). The Darkest regions of the image is the space outside the phantom, which is

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covered with black dots representing air material (Refer section 3.4.2. World material was set as air). The biggest circle, which includes in it three smaller circles represents water. In descending order, the 3 circles represent bone, aluminium and titanium respectively. It can be clearly noticed that air has the highest hit count and titanium has the lowest hit count.

ROOT results of cylinder phantom

Figure 4.2: ROOT simulation results of the water cylinder

A well defined cylinder geometry can be observed in Figure 4.2. This image is obtained by irradiating the cylinder phantom (refer section 3.4.2, Figure 3.18) with three million X-ray photons, which is one million X-ray photons less compared to the one used for AWBAT simulation. The left and right side boundaries of the cylinder in the image appear to have less hits compared to the inner and outer regions of the water cylinder phantom. The center part of the phantom has lower hit intensities than its sides but higher than intensities of the upper and lower regions of the cylinder phantom.

Gate-lab XCAT simulation results

Figure 4.3: Illustration of the GATE simulation results of the patient realistic XCAT phantom

Figure 4.3 shows the simulation results of the XCAT phantom (refer section 3.4.2, Figure 3.17) for only one projection. It was carried out on Gate-lab platform for cluster computing (refer to subsection 3.3.4) with 500 billion primaries. The simulations were split into 500 smaller simulations to run them in parallel and thus reduce simulation time. The raw data from Gate-lab was then processed with the assistance of Matlab software. Figure 4.3 shows the image result of the simulation. The dark regions of the XCAT simulation image indicate regions of low photon hit counts, while the brighter regions indicate

Figure 4.4: Illustration of the axial, sagittal and coronal planes of the XCAT

high photon hit counts. The bottom left side of the image show comparative higher hit intensities than other parts of the image. Slightly towards the right side from the image center, vertical line of dark boxes extend vertically downwards the bottom of the image. This resembles the sagittal view shown in Figure 4.4.

Gate-lab Water cylinder simulation results

Figure 4.5: Simulation results of a water cylinder at 0°, 45° and 90° (left to right)

The water cylinder simulations executed at 0°, 45° and 90° rotations show results (Figure 4.5) that have great resemblance to measurement results (Figure 4.8) obtained using Artis Zeego CBCT scanner with a real water cylinder (see section 3.4.2, Figure 3.18). The 0° image, depicts a dark circle at its center. The 45° tilt exposes lesser material at the upper and lower parts of the cylinder to the X-ray photons. For this reason, the 45° measurement simulation results show brighter top and bottom regions of the cylinder. On the other hand, the center has higher grey values compared to the upper and lower parts of the 45° tilted water container due to the material thickness at the center. In 90°

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cylinder simulation, the cylinder is upright and is of uniform colour unlike that of the 45°. However, at the corners of the cylinder, the circular edges are observed. The edges have a slightly higher intensity.

Figure 4.6: 3D CBCT image reconstruction of the water cylinder (top view) made out of 100 projections. One projection at every 3.6° rotation.

Figure 4.7: 3D CBCT image reconstruction of the water cylinder (side view) made out of 100 projections. One projection at every 3.6° rotation.

4.2 Measurement results

Figure 4.8: Artis Zeego CBCT scanner measurement results of the water container at 0° , 45° and 90° C-arm angles.(subsection 3.4.1, Figure 3.12)

The geometrical settings of the water container phantom that were used for developing a replica of it in GATE and for the Artis Zeego CBCT measurements can be referred to in section section 3.4.2 (Table 3.3). The measurement results of the water container at 0° , 45° and 90° as seen in Figure 4.8 are obtained using Artis Zeego scanner. These images are similar to the ones obtained through GATE simulations (refer Figure 4.5). However, there are little differences that can be noticed especially in the 90° angle image. For example the lid on the top of the water container, the water bubble (seen top right of the cylinder), the airspace between the cylinder and the carbon fiber operation table (see operation table in subsection 3.4.1, Figure 3.12).

Figure 4.9: 3D CBCT reconstructed image (top view) of the water container. obtained from 360 projections. One projection per one degree rotation.

Figure 4.10: 3D CBCT reconstructed image (side view) of the water container. obtained from 360 projections. One projection per one degree rotation.

4.3 Discussion

The results of the sanity checks, which were performed on AWBAT and water cylinder phantom were obtained using ROOT. ROOT images show only two colours: white and black, while the Gate-lab simulation result images show different shades of grey after being processed using Matlab software, where energies are given different grey values. The difference between the two result types is due to the varying output modes: imageCT and ROOT available in GATE. The imageCT output is processes hit data as per the digitizer structure and produces pixel wise output. In simulation results obtained using ROOT, the viewer can distinguish the type of material in the image based on the intensity of white or black dots. Higher the density of the material brighter the region. As mentioned earlier the white refers to no hits. High density materials like bone do not allow the penetration of the X-ray photons and as a result, only little hits is observable. For this reason, areas right behind high density materials appear brighter (has low hit counts) compared to low density materials because X-rays are able to penetrate through easily. In Figure 4.1, five different hit intensities are noticeable. A good correlation can be identified between density of the material and the hit counts on the ROOT image. Air has highest hit count, followed by water, bone, aluminium and titanium. Titanium has the least hit counts because of its opaqueness to X-ray photons. The difference in hit counts outside the phantom regions between Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2 is due to the difference in the X-ray photon numbers with which both the phantoms were simulated. Figure 4.2 was simulated with three million photons, whereas Figure 4.1 was simulated with four million photons. Through the simulation results obtained using ROOT, the implementation of X-ray interactions with different materials were validated.

For XCAT (Figure 4.3), cylinder simulations (Figure 4.5) and measurement simulation (Figure 4.8) the intensity range of the resulting simulation output just like a normal radiological image is expressed within a given range between a minimum and a maximum grey value. However, simulation results obtained as shown above is complementary to the real radiological images in terms of grey values. Here, low intensities show low grey values (white), whereas high intensities show higher grey values (black). In the XCAT simulation results (Figure 4.3) the vertebral column can be noticed on the right side of the image. The slightly curling dark structures extending from the right top corner diagonally towards the left are the rib bones seen mostly towards the top and middle areas of the image. The rib bones extending downwards as seen in the extreme right part of the image are the rib bones of the other side of the body. The intestine can be seen at the lower left side of the image. The stomach and the liver is quite hard to identify. It can be guessed

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out that the region just above the intestine, at the center left of the image is the stomach and the dark region above the stomach from the left to the right side of the image, which has higher intensity contrast could be the liver. The thick high intensity line that runs from the top towards the bottom close to the vertebral column is the aorta. It is viewable due to the presence of contrast material inside the aorta. In XCAT image shows rough tissue boundaries. Such artefacts are easily viewable in areas of low grey values like the bottom left regions of the image (intestine region). These artefacts are more likely to be caused by the resolution of the XCAT phantom. The voxels of the XCAT phantom are bigger ($0.75 \times 0.75\text{mm}$) than that of the detector pixels (0.308×0.308). Despite the image artefacts, there is fine distinction that can be made between the different body tissues present in the image. The simulation results of the XCAT provides a proof-of principle for incorporation of digital phantom data into the GATE framework.

In the simulation of the water cylinder, the Gate capabilities of implementing system rotation could be adapted to simulate a rotating CBCT system. The 3D CBCT image reconstructions made of 100 projections shown in Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7 have usual CBCT artefacts as well as artefacts caused due to lower number of projections. The higher the number of projections the better is the reconstructed 3D image, assuming the same number of photons per projection. In Figure 4.6 the reconstructed image does not show a perfect circular base area of the cylinder. The circle has sharp edges at the intersection points between the left and right cylinder arcs, which means missing projections. Such artefacts can in parts be corrected by using iterative reconstruction methods. Ring artefacts, which appear because of rotation of a defective detector element, are nowhere to be seen neither in the XCAT simulations nor in the cylinder simulations. This is expected as GATE simulations can't have a single detector element that is malfunctioning. In Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7 cupping artefacts are seen. The edges appear brighter than the inner regions. Cupping artefacts is mostly caused due to beam hardening. Beam hardening is common with polychromatic X-ray sources. As the X-ray passes through the body, low energy X-ray photons are attenuated more easily than the high energy photons. Beam hardening correction removes variation in grey values not associated with density. 3D image reconstructions from the simulated projection data was possible. These images were impaired by common imaging artifacts which can be accounted for in the future by increasing the number of projections and using iterative reconstruction methods.

Particle simulations consume plenty of time. In order to reduce the simulation time the number of pixels in the detector was reduced by half. It was set to 1240×960 pixels. The reduction of the number of pixels while keeping the original pixel size of 0.154mm means smaller detector size. Therefore the pixel size was doubled (0.308mm) to maintain

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the actual geometry of the flat detector ($382 \times 296\text{mm}$). The increase in pixel size in this case can substantially decrease the simulation time, because the detector geometry initialization takes less time. To get smoother image with no edge artefacts and fine tissue boundaries, the number of pixels should be doubled and pixel size reduced by half. The increase in number of pixels to 2480×1920 pixels would mean generating about five million pixels, this leads to longer simulation time.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

In this thesis, a CBCT simulation framework based on the MC method was developed using GATE. The framework enables the simulation of accelerated CBCT projections using Gate-Lab computer cluster grid. In particular the framework is able to simulate circular CBCT source-detector orbits and can incorporate patient anatomy. A Mersenne Twister PRNG was preferred to carry out the random number generation because of its long period and its ability to generate statistically uniform distribution of values. Artis Zeego CBCT scanner specifications of the detector, X-ray source, object positioning etc. were modelled in GATE and each of these components was assigned a separate macro file. In total, the CBCT simulation framework consists of 12 separate macro modules. The macros were called from the main macro for execution. The order of their execution is set in accordance to the GATE architecture.

Simulations with reduced number of photons were performed for validating the X-ray interactions and the geometrical settings of different materials in the CBCT setup. Moreover, two CBCT simulations with realistic X-ray photon count were executed. In the first simulation, a patient realistic cardio-torso XCAT phantom was simulated using 500 billion X-rays for one projection as a proof-of-principle to show that the framework is capable of incorporating digital body phantoms. In the second simulation using a water cylinder phantom, the same number of photons was split between 100 projections. Here, the capabilities of implementing a rotating CBCT system was demonstrated. The 3D image of the water cylinder simulation that was carried out with limited number projections was obtained using analytical CBCT reconstruction by means of Matlab. The water cylinder simulation results showed resemblance to the Artis Zeego measurement results. In order to accelerate these bulky simulations, Gate-lab cluster computing platform was used. Each simulation was split into 100s of smaller jobs for parallelization and acceleration of the simulation process. In this manner, original simulation time of a few weeks could be reduced to only 3 days using Gate-lab.

Carrying out simulations using image-quality phantoms can help in validating the image quality. For instance, the effect of reduction of X-ray photons on the image quality can

5 Conclusion and Outlook

be analyzed. Thereby understanding how low the X-ray number can be reduced without compensating beyond diagnostically acceptable image. In this manner the implementation of the concept of ALADA "as low as diagnostically acceptable" would be possible. With the assistance of an inbuilt Gate tool known as actor, information such as energy deposition and number of particles received in a given volume can be collected. The actor has to be attached to a particular volume in order to obtain the imparted imparted in that volume. For example, attaching the actor to the intestine region of the XCAT voxelized phantom would enable us to calculate dose to the intestine. Additionally, the dose actors can be attached to the area surrounding CBCT setup to quantify and visualize scattered radiations. Ultimately, this simulation framework can be extended to simulate CBCT imaging with alternative source-detector trajectories to investigate their influence on the resulting image quality. Alternative trajectories have already been implemented [48] in an in-house measurement setup and can provide experimental validation.

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